

ENTREPRENEURSHIP EDUCATION TEACHING METHODOLOGIES: UNIVERSITY STUDENTS' PREFERENCES IN NIGERIA

Mopelola Omotayo AYO-SOBOWALE (Ph.D)

Department of Educational Management, Faculty of Education
Lagos State University, Ojo
mayosobowale@gmail.com

Cite (APA): Ayo-Sobowale M. O. (2024). Entrepreneurship Education Teaching Methodologies: University Students' Preferences in Nigeria. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Nigerian Economy* 4(1)

Abstract

Entrepreneurship education prepares youths to be responsible and enterprising individuals, who become entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial thinkers by exposing them to real life learning experiences. Therefore, teaching methods play significant roles in the development of future entrepreneurs. Also, for a student to become a successful entrepreneur, it is essential to find the most effective method/s for the teachers to support entrepreneurship education and find the ideal connection between the needs of the students and the right choice of teaching method/s. The main aim of this study was to determine the preferential method/s of teaching by the students in entrepreneurship education. The study adopted a descriptive design and it covered universities in South-West Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria where the students must have taken entrepreneurship education as a course or General Studies (GST). For this study, the researcher used a purposive and multi-stage sampling methodology where only 3 states namely: Lagos, Ogun and Oyo States with 23 universities with a population of 80,740 undergraduate students and a sample of 3,160 undergraduate students were used respectively. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions. Based on the research findings, the respondents agreed that the use of real-world experiences, business models and simulations, case studies, video clippings and mentoring were preferred, which invariably improved the students' entrepreneurial participation.

Keywords: Entrepreneur, Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship Education, Students' Preferences, Teaching Methodologies.

Introduction

At present, countries attach great importance to the role of innovation and entrepreneurship in promoting national economic development (Youssef et al., 2018). Entrepreneurship is a dynamic process of vision, change and creation. It requires to be taught for the transfer of its skill and knowledge from an expert to someone else. It involves an application of energy and passion towards the creation of an enterprise and this includes: willingness to take calculated risks, team work, having creative skill to marshal needed resources, fundamental skill of building solid business plan; and finally, having the vision to recognize opportunity where others see chaos, contradiction, and confusion.

Policy makers and scholars are increasingly interested in student entrepreneurship (Meoli et al., 2020; Lackeus, 2015), which is defined as a “new venture creation” by university students and recent graduates (Piva, 2020).

There are several reasons behind such interest in ventures created by students (i) have a large economic impact and contribute to economic impact and contribute to job creation (Astebro et al., 2011), (ii) represent a mechanism for commercializing the knowledge generated within universities (Shah and Pankeh, 2014), (iii) develop and commercialize innovative solutions, which address social needs (Astebro and Hoos, 2021; Hahn, 2020; Sieger et al., 2016), and (iv) represent a valuable career option for young people in a time where youth unemployment affects many countries (Roman and Maxim, 2017). Today, universities are regarded as the main actors and triggers of technological change and innovation, as well as important tools of economic and social development and knowledge production (Genc et al., 2020). More and more are designing a university ecosystem (Wright et al., 2017). That supports student entrepreneurship by stimulating students’ entrepreneurial attitudes and skills and facilitate venture creation activities (Fyen et al., 2019) In this regard Entrepreneurship Education (EE)) constitutes a central pillar within the university ecosystem for student entrepreneurship (Gibb et al., 2018) in order to motivate and prepare students from different fields and levels of study (Fiore et al., 2019; Soutarsis et al., 2007) to pursue venture creation. Also, Mohd Aziz et al., (2018), stated that entrepreneurship is one of the subjects that students need to learn whether taking business or other programmes at the Institutions of Higher Learning (IHL) to instill entrepreneurship in daily lives through the curriculum at the IHL. Additionally, in the Global Student Entrepreneurship Report (2018), special emphasis was placed on the crucial impact of students’ entrepreneurship, both economically and socially. At the university stage, students define their future perspectives in the short and medium terms, with entrepreneurship becoming a job option that is increasingly valued by them (Ofstedal et al., 2018).

With this paradigm shift in the emergence of knowledge-economy, Nigerian universities have shifted from the traditional pedagogical role to incorporate innovation and entrepreneurship which are critical factors in enhancing development in a modern economy (Jackson, 2015; Ayo-sobowale, 2021). The development of entrepreneurship education fills the gap of higher education, and it develops students’ skills, abilities and knowledge base (Turner and Gianiodis, 2018). This

is in line with Fayolle et al's., (2014) view that entrepreneurship education is an effective means to internalize various experiences, knowledge, values, and norms to students. Entrepreneurship education is designed to inculcate competences, skills, attitudes, values and abilities essential for recognizing business opportunities while developing the creative instincts in students to make them eager to start their own businesses. Therefore, entrepreneurship education in universities is great significance to the sustainable development of developing countries, and Nigeria is not an exception (Ayo-sobowale, 2021).

Statement of the problem

The most prominent problem facing Nigeria is how to get the youths gainfully employed. Greater number of graduates are still searching for employment or being underemployed. The overall unemployment in Nigeria has increased to 27.1% as at 2020 of the 2nd Quarter, meaning that about 21.7 million of Nigerians remained unemployed (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). Nigeria's unemployment rate was 23.1% in the 3rd Quarter of 2018, confirming its increase by 4% between then and the Quarter of 2020. Nigeria's youths remain the hardest hit by unemployment with over 24.5 million (13.1million unemployed and 11.3 million underemployed) youths aged between 15 and 34 years (Nigeria Economic Alert, 2020). Also, the challenge faced by the graduates stemmed from the training they received, full of too much theory and little practical content which cannot equip them with desirable skills and competencies required for job creation and self-employment (Pitan and Adedeji, 2012 cited in Ayo-sobowale, 2021).

Also, the university curriculum is found to be lacking in content and quality, largely theoretical, overloaded, obsolete and disconnected from the labour market and therefore inadequate to attend to the needs of the 21st century students (Bamiro, Adedeji & Pitan, 2012; Madou, 2015 cited in Ayo-sobowale, 2021). The inappropriateness of the curriculum and course contents is a challenging issue in entrepreneurship education and students are not well equipped with entrepreneurship key competencies such as creative and innovative skills that would help them in starting and running their own businesses (Zegeye, 2013; Edokpolor and Somorin, 2017).

Furthermore, the most argued and relevant challenges of entrepreneurship education consist of different pedagogical approaches, learning strategies and knowledge creation proceses (Fayolle, 2013; Secondo et al., 2016; Ndou, 2021). A cursory look at the teaching methods in Nigerian universities shows that the teaching methodologies have not changed from the old system of

theoretically based, delivered through the normal classroom setting which does not provide practical clue. The teaching/pedagogical should enable the students to see socio-economic problems as challenges that could be translated into viable and feasible business opportunities (Sahlberg, 2010). The teaching methodologies to be adopted should focus on students' capacity i.e. the ability to benefit from the opportunities offered which they will be faced with (Bauha et al., 2022). Norasmah et al., (2009), stated that entrepreneurship education would be more effective if the learning methods utilize real experiences as an entrepreneur. Also, Volkman et al., (2009), stated that multiple approaches and interactive teaching methods are necessary to promote creativity, innovation, critical thinking, opportunity recognition, and social awareness.

Research Questions

- 1) What are the teaching methodologies used in the teaching-learning of Entrepreneurship Education in South-West of Nigeria?
- 2) What are the students' preferences in the teaching-learning methodologies of Entrepreneurship Education in South-West of Nigeria?

Methodology

The study employed the descriptive research survey design. The study area was South-West of Nigeria comprising of Oyo, Ogun, Ekiti, Osun, Ondo, and Lagos States. The population of the study was 239,512 final year undergraduate students in 54 Federal, State and Private Universities who must have taken Entrepreneurship Education as a course or as General Studies (GST). Three states were randomly selected namely Lagos, Ogun and Oyo states respectively, there are 23 universities with a population of 124,852 undergraduate students. Three universities (Federal, State and Private) were randomly selected from the three states making a total of 9 universities with a population of 80,740 final year undergraduate students; the sample was 3,160 which were determined using the table by Krejcie and Morgan (1970). The study used a multi-stage sampling to get the required sample. This study employed both convenience and purposive sampling technique. The research instrument was a structured questionnaire on a 7-point Likert scale, with 9 items, a total of 3,160 questionnaires were distributed, and a total of 78 (2.5%) questionnaires were incompletely filled due to errors. Therefore, a total of 3082 questionnaires were used for this study.

A test re-test was used to establish the reliability of the questionnaire which was administered to 40 respondents, using the Cronbach's Alpha for internal consistency using SPSS 27 for reliability procedure, a reliability of 0.797 was obtained. For the data analysis, mean value of 4.0 and above were considered accepted, while less scores than 4.0 were considered rejected.

Table 1: Response to students preferences of teaching methodologies (items 1-9)

	<i>SD</i>	<i>D</i>	<i>TD</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>TA</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>SA</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>
	%	%	%	%	%	%	%		
The instructor did a good job in making the entrepreneurship education course relevant to the real-world	214 6.9%	99 3.2%	110 3.6%	118 3.8%	580 18.8%	1094 35.5%	867 28.1%	5.43	1.695
The instructors are experienced in teaching the courses	83 2.7%	242 7.9%	129 4.2%	124 4.0%	542 17.6%	1061 34.4%	901 29.2%	5.46	1.627
The methodologies introduced by the instructors for the entrepreneurship education courses are very interesting	75 2.4%	149 4.8%	248 8.0%	97 3.1%	602 19.5%	1115 36.2%	796 25.8%	5.44	1.542
The instructors teach a comprehensive business model during the course	75 2.4%	232 7.5%	122 4.0%	116 3.8%	618 20.1%	1075 34.9%	844 27.4%	5.46	1.581
The instructors stimulate my interest through case-studies	145 4.7%	131 4.3%	143 4.6%	110 3.6%	591 19.2%	1137 36.9%	825 26.8%	5.46	1.608
The instructors teach through hands on project/assignment	77 2.5%	209 6.8%	165 5.4%	94 3.0%	604 19.6%	1044 33.9%	889 28.8%	5.47	1.588
The stories of great entrepreneurs in video clippings are shown in the classroom to motivate the students for business venture creation.	102 3.3%	188 6.1%	143 4.6%	113 3.7%	557 18.1%	1118 36.3%	861 27.9%	5.48	1.598
The instructors use the business simulation games in motivating the students	89 2.9%	204 6.6%	142 4.6%	137 4.4%	546 17.7%	1071 34.8%	893 29.0%	5.48	1.602
Adequate guidance of young entrepreneurs (mentoring)helped in creating my ideas	145 4.7%	185 6.0%	157 5.1%	107 3.5%	732 23.8%	866 28.1%	890 28.9%	5.35	1.686

The result from Table 1 above which measured the responses of the respondents to teaching methodologies showed that 214 (6.9%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with item 1, ***“The instructor did a good job in making the entrepreneurship education course relevant to the real-world”***, 99 (3.2%) further disagreed, 110 (3.6%) totally disagreed, and 118 (3.8%) were neutral. However, 580 (18.8%) totally agreed, 1094 (35.5%) were the majority of the respondents that agreed, while 867 (28.1%) of the respondents strongly agreed with item 1. Therefore, item 1, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.43$, $SD = 1.70$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Hence, majority of the respondents accepted item 1, that, the instructor did a good job in making the entrepreneurship education course relevant to the real-word.

Also, 83 (2.7%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with the item 2, ***“The instructors are experienced in teaching the courses”***, 242 (7.9%) further disagreed, 129 (4.2%) totally disagreed, and 124 (4.0%) were neutral. However, 542 (17.6%) totally agreed, 1061 (34.4%) were the majority of the respondents that agreed, while 901 (29.2%) of the respondents strongly agreed with item 2. Therefore, item 2, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.46$, $SD = 1.63$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Majority of the respondents accepted item 2, that the instructors are experienced in teaching the courses.

Also, 75 (2.4%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with item 3, ***“The methodologies introduced by the instructors for the entrepreneurship education courses are very interesting”***, 149 (4.8%) further disagreed, 248 (8.0%) totally disagreed, and 97 (3.1%) were neutral. However, 602 (19.5%) totally agreed, 1115 (36.2%) were the majority of the respondents that agreed, while 796 (25.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed with item 3. Therefore, item 3, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.44$, $SD = 1.54$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Thus, item 3 was accepted by majority of the respondents’ that the methodologies introduced by the instructors for the entrepreneurship education courses are very interesting

About 75 (2.4%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with item 4, ***“The instructors teach a comprehensive business model during the course”***, 232 (7.5%) further disagreed, 122 (4.0%) totally disagreed, and 116 (3.8%) were neutral. However, 618 (20.1%) totally agreed, 1075

(34.9%) were of the majority of the respondents that agreed, while 844 (27.4%) of the respondents strongly agreed with item 4. Therefore, item 4, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.46$, $SD = 1.61$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Majority of the respondents accepted item 4 that the instructors teach a comprehensive business model during the course.

A total of 145 (4.7%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with item 5, "***The instructors stimulate my interest through case-studies***", 131 (4.3%) further disagreed, 143 (4.6%) totally disagreed, and 110 (3.6%) were neutral. However, 591 (19.2%) totally agreed, 1137 (36.9%) were the majority of the respondents that agreed, while 825 (26.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed with item 5. Therefore, item 5, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.46$, $SD = 1.61$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Hence item 5 that the instructors stimulate my interest through case studies was accepted by majority of the respondents.

A total of 77 (2.5%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with item 6, "***The instructors teach through hands on project/assignment***", 209 (6.8%) further disagreed, 165 (5.4%) totally disagreed, and 94 (3.0%) were neutral. However, 604 (19.6%) totally agreed, 1044 (33.9%) were the majority of the respondents that agreed, while 889 (28.8%) of the respondents strongly agreed with item 6. Therefore, item 6, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.47$, $SD = 1.59$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Thus majority of the respondents accepted item 6 that the instructors teach through hands on project/assignment.

A total of 102 (3.3%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with item 7, "***The stories of great entrepreneurs in video clippings are shown in the classroom to motivate the students for business venture creation***", 188 (6.1%) further disagreed, 143 (4.6%) totally disagreed, and 113 (3.7%) were neutral. However, 557 (18.1%) totally agreed, 1118 (36.3%) were the majority of the respondents that agreed, while 861 (27.9%) of the respondents strongly agreed with item 7. Therefore, item 7, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.48$, $SD = 1.60$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Since item 7 was

accepted, majority of the respondents' sees the stories of great entrepreneurs in video clippings shown in the classroom to motivate the students for business venture creation.

A total of 89 (2.9%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with item 8, "*The instructors use the business simulation games in motivating the students*", 204 (6.6%) further disagreed, 142 (4.6%) totally disagreed, and 137 (4.4%) were neutral. However, 546 (17.7%) totally agreed, 1071 (34.8%) were the majority of the respondents that agreed, while 893 (29.0%) of the respondents strongly agreed with item 8. Therefore, item 8, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.48$, $SD = 1.60$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Majority of the respondents accepted item 8, that, the instructors use the business simulation games in motivating the students.

Lastly, 145 (4.7%) of the respondents strongly disagreed with item 9, "*Adequate guidance of young entrepreneurs (mentoring) has helped in creating my ideas*", 185 (6.0%) further disagreed, 157 (5.1%) totally disagreed, and 107 (3.5%) were neutral. However, 732 (23.8%) totally agreed, 866 (28.1%) of the respondents agreed while 890 (28.9%) were the majority of the respondents that strongly agreed with item 9. Therefore, item 9, was not rejected as the mean ($M = 5.35$, $SD = 1.69$) was greater than the cut off mean ($M = 4.0$) for acceptance or rejection of items on a seven-point Likert scale. Lastly, majority of the respondents accepted item 9, that, adequate guidance of young entrepreneurs (mentoring) has helped in creating my ideas. All the methodologies used were in line with the studies of Arasti et al (2012); Tasmin (2012); Esmin et al (2015); and Ayo-sobowale (2021). The above analysis was supported with the works of Esmi et al (2015); Duval-Couetil et al (2016); Okoye (2017); Mandel & Noyes (2016); Andoh et al (2019); and Ayo-sobowale (2021).

Major findings of the study

With regards to the teaching –learning methodologies of entrepreneurship education, both traditional methodologies such as classroom lectures, selected reading textbooks, seminars and assignments; and the active methods (innovative methods) such as games and competition, presentations, field works, business planning were used.

With the study, the students' preferences were business models, case-studies, group projects, business ventures/creation, and simulation games, mentoring and problem-solving.

Conclusion and Recommendations

There are no single entrepreneurship education teaching methodologies used in universities. All teaching-learning methodologies were used in the university which leads to student's entrepreneurial participation.

It is therefore recommended that Active methodologies (innovative teaching) will provide students the experiences of simulated new venture decision making and develop their skills in decision-making. All these innovative teaching methodologies are considered to be more effective methods of teaching.

References

- Arasti, Z., Falavarjani, M. K. and Imanipour, N. (2012) 'A Study of Teaching Methods in Entrepreneurship Education for Graduate Students', *Higher Education Studies*, Vol. 2, No. 1, pp. 2–10. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/hes.v2n1p2>
- Andah R, Hauwa LA, Isichei E 2019. Entrepreneurial education and venture creation: An emerging economy perspective, *International Journal of Scientific Research in Social Sciences and Management Studies*, 4(2): 184-200
- Audu R, Kamin Y, Musta'amal AHB, Sukri M 2014. Assessment of the teaching methods that influence the acquisition of practical skills. *Asian Social Science*. DOI:10.5539/ASS.V10N21P35
- Åstebro, Thomas, and Florian Hoos. 2021. Impact measurement based on repeated randomized control trials: The case of a training program to encourage social entrepreneurship. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal* 15: 254–78.
- Åstebro, Thomas, Jing Chen, and Perter Thompson. 2011. Stars and misfits: Self-employment and labor market frictions. *Management Science* 57: 1999–2017.
- Ayo-Sobowale Mopelola Omotayo (2021). Effects of entrepreneurship education on entrepreneurial intentions of undergraduate students in selected universities in south-west of Nigeria.
- Balan, S. M. (2014) 'Methods and means used in teaching entrepreneurship in high school can improve entrepreneurial skills', *International Journal of Management*, Vol. 5, No. 7, pp. 51–61.
- Bamiro O, Adedeji, O. Pitan.,(2013) Transforming Nigeria economy through sustainable financing of higher education in O.Oni (Ed) challenges and prospects in Africa Education System. USA and Canada: Trafford Publishing INC,pp 283-395

- Banha, Francisco, Luís Serra Coelho, and Adão Flores. 2022. Entrepreneurship Education: A Systematic Literature Review and Identification of an Existing Gap in the Field. *Education Sciences* 12: 336.
- Bridge S, Hegarty C, Porter S 2010. Rediscovering Enterprise: Developing Appropriate University Entrepreneurship Education. *Education and Training*, 52(8/9):722-734. From <<http://www.emeraldinsight.com/0040-0912.htm>> (Retrieved on 22 February 2022).
- Cui, J., Sun, J. and Bell, R. (2019) ‘The impact of entrepreneurship education on the entrepreneurial mindset of college students in China: The mediating role of inspiration and the role of educational attributes’, *The International Journal of Management Education*, 100296. <https://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijme.2019.04.001>
- Duval-Couetil, N.,Shartrand ,A, and Reed, T.(2016). The role of entrepreneurship program models and experiential activities on engineering students’ outcomes. *Advanced Engineering & Education*, 5,1-27
- European Commission. 2021a. A Guide to Fostering Entrepreneurship Education. Five Key Actions towards a Digital, Green and Resilient Europe. European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). B-1049, Brussels. Available online: <http://www.eehub.eu/component/attachments/?task=download&id=1560:EA0921266E> NN (accessed on 18 December 2022).
- Eesley, Charles E., and Yong Suk Lee. 2020. Do university entrepreneurship programs promote entrepreneurship? *Strategic Management Journal* 42: 833–61.
- Esmi K, Marzoughi R, Torkzadeh J 2015. Teaching learning methods of an entrepreneurship curriculum. *Journal of Advances in Medical Education and Professionalism*,3(4): 172-177.
- Fatoki , O.(2014): An Examination of the teaching methods and learning process in entrepreneurship education . *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(23),pg 512
- Fayolle, Alain. 2013. Personal views on the future of entrepreneurship education. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development* 25: 692–701.
- Fayolle, Alain, Caroline Verzat, and RobertWapshott. 2016. In Quest of Legitimacy, the Theoretical and Methodological Foundations of Entrepreneurship Education Research. *International Small Business Journal* 34. Available online: <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/10.1177/0266242616649250> (accessed on 18 December 2022).
- Fayolle, Alain, Benoît Gailly, and Narjisse Lassas-Clerc. 2006. Assessing the impact of entrepreneurship education programmes: A new methodology. *Journal of European Industrial Training* 30: 701–20. Available online: <https://www.emerald.com/insight/content/doi/10.1108/03090590610715022/full/html> (accessed on 18 December 2022).

- Fiore, Eleonora, Giuliano Sansone, and Emilio Paolucci. 2019. Entrepreneurship education in a multidisciplinary environment: Evidence from an entrepreneurship programme held in Turin. *Administrative Sciences* 9: 28.
- Fyen, Wim, Koenraad Debackere, Maria Olivares, Roger Gfrörer, Erik Stam, Ben Mumby-Croft, and Laura Keustermans. 2019. Student Entrepreneurship at Research-Intensive Universities: From a Peripheral Activity toward a New Mainstream. League of European Research Universities, Pushing the Frontiers of Innovative Research. Leuven: LERU.
- Gibb A 2006. Towards the Entrepreneurial University: Entrepreneurship Education as a Lever For Change, *NCGE Policy Paper Series*, Birmingham.
- Gibb, Allan, Andrea R. Hofer, and Magnus Klofsten. 2018. The Entrepreneurial and Innovative Higher Education Institution: A Review of the Concepts and Its Relevance Today. HEInnovate. Available online: https://heinnovate.eu/sites/default/files/heinnovate_concept_note.pdf
- Hahn, Davide, Tommaso Minola, Giulio Bosio, and Lucio Cassia. 2020. The impact of entrepreneurship education on university students' entrepreneurial skills: A family embeddedness perspective. *Small Business Economics* 55: 257–82.
- Jackson, T,C (2015) Entrepreneurship training in tertiary education. It's development and transfer Local Economy, 1-19 <https://journals.sagepub.wanldoi/abs/10.1177/0269094215589142>
- Karlsson, Tomas, and Kåre Moberg. 2013. Improving perceived entrepreneurial abilities through education: Exploratory testing of an entrepreneurial self-efficacy scale in a pre-post setting. *The International Journal of Management Education* 11: 1–11.
- Lackéus, Martin. 2015. Entrepreneurship in Education: What, Why, When, How, Entrepreneurship 360. Background Paper. OECD Center for Entrepreneurship. Paris: OECD
- Lackéus, Martin. 2020. Comparing the impact of three different experiential approaches to entrepreneurship in education. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Behavior and Research* 26: 937–71.
- Lyons, Elizabeth, and Laurina Zhang. 2018. Who does (not) benefit from entrepreneurship programs? *Strategic Management Journal* 39:85–112.
- Mandel , R and Noyes, E.(2016). Survey of experiential entrepreneurship education among top undergraduates entrepreneurship programs. *Education and Training*, 58(2) , 164-178
- Meoli, Azzurra, Riccardo Fini, Maurizio Sobrero, and Johan Wiklund. 2020. How entrepreneurial intentions influence entrepreneurial career choices: The moderating influence of social context. *Journal of Business Venturing* 35: 105982

- Mohd Aziz, N.E., Harnn, N., Mohd Esa, M., Yaacob, M.R., & Ab Rahman, A.A.(2018). Pendidikan keusa hawanan di institute pengagan tinggi(IPT) dalam melahirkan usahawan Berjaya di Malaysia. *Journal of Business Innovation*, 3, 73-85
- Mwasalwiba, E. S. (2010) 'Entrepreneurship education: a review of its objectives, teaching methods, and impact indicators', *Education and Training*, Vol. 52, No. 1, pp. 20–47. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/00400911011017663>
- Nabi, Ghulam, Andreas Walmsley, Francisco Liñán, Imran Akhtar, and Charles Neame. 2018. Does entrepreneurship education in the first year of higher education develop entrepreneurial intentions? The role of learning and inspiration. *Studies in Higher Education* 43: 452–67.
- Naia, Ana, Rui Baptista, Carlos Januário, and Virginia Trigo. 2014. A systematization of the literature on entrepreneurship education: Challenges and emerging solutions in the entrepreneurial classroom. *Industry and Higher Education* 28: 79–96.
- National Bureau of Statistics 2020. Labor Force Statistics: Unemployment and Underemployment Report: Abridged Labour Force Survey Under Covid-19. From <https://www.nigerianstat.gov.ng/pdfuploads/Q2_2020_Unemployment_Report.pdf> (Retrieved on 12 February 2022).
- Neck, H. M. and Greene, P. G. (2011) 'Entrepreneurship Education: Known Worlds and New Frontiers', *Journal of Small Business Management*, Vol. 49, No. 1, pp. 55–70. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-627x.2010.00314.x>
- Ndou, V., Mele, G. and Vecchio, P. D. (2019) 'Entrepreneurship education in tourism: An investigation among European Universities', *Journal of Hospitality, Leisure, Sport & Tourism Education*, No. 25, 100175, pp. 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhlste.2018.10.003>
- Ndou, Valentina. 2021. Social Entrepreneurship Education: A Combination of Knowledge Exploitation and Exploration Processes *Administrative Sciences* 11: 112.
- Norasmah, O,Buti, O., and Othman, S.H(2017). The perceptions of Public University Students of Entrepreneurship Education in Malaysia . *International Business Management*, 11(4):865-897,2017:ISSN: 1993-5250.1 pp 865-873
- Oftedal, E M., Lakovleva, T.A., Foss, L.(2018). University context matter: An institutional perspective on entrepreneurial intentions of students. *Education and Training*, 2018. 60,873-890
- Okoye AC 2017. Entrepreneurship education: A panacea for graduate unemployment in Nigeria. *Online Journal of Arts, Management and Social Sciences*, 2(1):56-63.
- Oksanen, Lea, Elena Oikkonen, and Timo Pihkala. 2022. Adopting Entrepreneurship Education—Teachers Professional Development. *Entrepreneurship Education and Pedagogy*, 1–23

- Roman, Eodora, and Alexandru Maxim. 2017. National culture and higher education as pre-determining factors of student entrepreneurship. *Studies in Higher Education* 42: 993–1014.
- Sahlberg , P. (2010). Rethinking Accountability in a Knowledge Society. *Journal of Educational Change* ,11(1):45-61
- Secundo, Giustina, Valentina Ndou, and Pasquale Del Vecchio. 2016. Challenges for instilling entrepreneurial mindset in scientists and engineers: What works in European universities? *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management* 13: 1640012
- Shane, Scott, and Sankaran Venkataraman. 2000. The promise of entrepreneurship as a field of research. *Academy of Management Review* 25: 217–26.
- Shah, Sonali K., and Emily C. Pahnke. 2014. Parting the ivory curtain: Understanding how universities support a diverse set of startups. *The Journal of Technology Transfer* 39: 780–92
- Shah DK, Campus S 2021. Conceptualising and defining pedagogy. *IOSR Journal of Research and Method in Education*, 11(1): 6-29.
- Sirelkhatim F, Gangi Y 2015. Entrepreneurship education: A systematic literature review of curricula contents and teaching methods. *Cogent Business and Management*, 2:1. DOI: 10.1080/23311975.2015.1052034.
- Souitaris, Vangelis, Stefania Zerbinati, and Andreas Al-Laham. 2007. Do entrepreneurship programmes raise entrepreneurial intention of science and engineering students? The effect of learning, inspiration and resources. *Journal of Business Venturing* 22: 566–91.
- Wright, Mike, Donald S. Siegel, and Philippe Mustar. 2017. An emerging ecosystem for student start-ups. *The Journal of Technology Transfer* 42: 909–22.